

Open Data

Open Data are “non-private and non-confidential data made available through public means, without restricting its use or dissemination” (Purnama Jati et al. 2022).

The Open Data Movement

Born in the context of the Open Government Movement (Attard et al. 2015), the Open Data Movement seeks to improve democratic governance and participation by lobbying governments to "make their machine-readable data discoverable, available, and downloadable through dedicated internet portals without costs to potential data users" (Dawes, Vidasova, and Parkhimovich 2016,15).

The Open Data Movement seeks to apply the principles of openness and accessibility to a wide range of data sources, including government data, scientific data, and various types of public and private sector information (Huijboom and van den Broek 2011).

Actors in the Open Date Movement aim to improve governance by increasing the transparency and accountability of data producers in the public and private sectors, empowering citizens, journalists, and civil society organizations to scrutinize the actions and decisions of governments, corporations, and other institutions (Worthy 2015).

Principles of Open Data

	Accessibility	Open Data should be easily accessible with minimal barriers to access.
	Usability	Open Data should be made available in machine-readable formats to enable easier processing and analysis, rather than proprietary or hard to use formats.
	Transparency	Open Data promotes transparency and accountability by enabling stakeholders to scrutinize information from governments, organizations, and institutions.
	Reusability	Open Data should be licensed in a way that allows for the free use, modification, and distribution of the data without restrictions.
	Timeliness	Open Data should be made available in a timely manner.

Difficulties facing Open Data

Ensuring **data quality/reliability**, which requires data curation, standardization, and validation processes.

Balancing openness and transparency with privacy and data security, considering the potential risks of making sensitive or personal information publically available.

Long-term sustainability of Open Data initiatives - ongoing investment in infrastructure, data management, and user support.

Encouraging **widespread engagement with and adoption of** Open Data initiatives and principles.

Technical barriers related to data formats, standards, and interoperability to ensure machine-readability and standardization.

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